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Numerical modeling for real-time hybrid simulation of wave flume moorings

Abilyn McConnell^a, Bryson Robertson^a

^aPacific Marine Energy Center (PMEC) 101 Kearney Hall, Oregon State University, Corvallis, OR 97331-3212

Abstract

The development and testing of wave energy converters (WECs) require accurate replication of mooring forces, which are challenging to model due to their nonlinear dynamics and due to the geometric constraints of wave flumes. Traditional methods, such as using springs, fall short in replicating real-world non-linear mooring forces and failure events. This research proposes a modern technique using hybrid simulation or hardware-in-the-loop (HIL) to simulate mooring line forces in real-time. A numerical model was developed using WEC-Sim and coupled with the lumped mass mooring software MoorDyn. Validation of the model will be performed using data from the Laboratory Upgrade Point Absorber (LUPA), which was recently tested at the O.H. Hinsdale Wave Lab. The validated model will be implemented in a real-time hybrid simulation using Simulink RealTime on a SpeedGoat, where calculated mooring forces are applied to a scaled WEC in a wave flume. This approach aims to enhance the fidelity of lab-scale WEC testing, providing a more accurate representation of mooring dynamics and enabling the testing of various mooring designs and conditions.

Keywords: wave energy converters; hybrid simulation; mooring dynamics; WEC-Sim; real-time testing

1. Introduction

As wave energy continues to grow as a field, the need for testing scaled devices also grows. Wave tank testing has become a standard for validating scale models of wave energy converters (WECs). While the physical geometries of these devices can be simply scaled, the mooring setup and forces are generally much harder to scale and accurately model. There are limited approaches to modeling the dynamics seen in moored devices. The standard and widely used approach is utilizing a spring or series of springs in an attempt to replicate some of the nonlinear forces applied by true full-depth mooring lines[1]. However, using springs can still be a time-consuming process when done correctly, requiring calculations to determine correct behavior and even then, are inaccurate at replicating dynamic mooring forces[2]. Springs (and all other current methods for replicating mooring forces on lab-scale WECs) cannot reproduce the real-world dynamics of mooring lines, fail to properly simulate nonlinear tension behaviors, and cannot be used to demonstrate failure events such as line breakage[3]. Additionally, more complex mooring configurations such as catenary moorings or use of mooring buoys cannot be replicated in wave tank testing. Therefore, to improve the fidelity of testing lab-scale WECs, it is critical to develop a modern-day technique for simulating mooring line forces. One proposed method is through hybrid simulation or hardware in the loop[4]. With this approach, a simulation is used in conjunction with a lab-scaled prototype in a real-time feedback loop to

introduce user-defined forces for a range of scenarios. This system could be used to test mooring effects with various mooring designs, water depths, line qualities, and more. A hybrid simulation approach could also be used to simulate extreme wave conditions or line-break scenarios. There has been some research into the feasibility of this hybrid simulation approach, but a prior lack of technology and equipment has limited the success of this approach[3]. Now, with today's technology, processing speed, and equipment, the possibility of this simulation approach is within reach.

2. Methodology

2.1 Model Development and Validation

The first step in this research was to develop a high-fidelity numerical model of a hydrodynamic body to later be used in the real-time loop. This involved creating a model of the body using WEC-Sim, an open-source simulation tool specifically designed for simulating WEC dynamics[5]. To accurately simulate the mooring forces, the WEC-Sim model was coupled with MoorDyn, an open-source lumped mass mooring dynamics software[6]. Unlike springs, MoorDyn is able to simulate complex and nonlinear behavior as is seen in true mooring line motions. Key parameters for the WEC and mooring lines were defined based on their respective physical characteristics. The model was tested under a range of wave periods and heights to identify and mitigate any numerical instabilities. This included refining the time-step size and ensuring that the numerical solver settings were optimized for the coupled WEC and mooring system.

Upon model completion, a validation study will be run. This simulation uses models of both the Laboratory Upgrade Point Absorber (LUPA) or a simpler flattened cylindrical body[7]. Both of these have been tested extensively in the O.H. Hinsdale Wave Lab. The same wave conditions, mooring setups, and test parameters used in these past experiments will be replicated in the simulations. This includes varying wave heights, periods, and mooring line configurations to cover a wide range of scenarios. The validation will focus on key response metrics such as mooring line tension, WEC displacement, and motion trajectories. An acceptable error range of 5-10% has been established, recognizing that while numerical models cannot perfectly replicate physical tests, they should closely approximate the observed behaviors. Specific benchmarks for validation will include the peak and average mooring line forces, the frequency and amplitude of WEC oscillations, and the overall stability of the mooring system. These benchmarks will help in quantifying the model's performance and identifying areas for improvement.

2.2 Real-Time Loop Development

Following the successful validation of the numerical model, the next phase of this research involves implementing and refining the real-time hybrid simulation of the WEC mooring system. Figure 1 shows the wave flume setup and illustrates the full-depth lines that will be simulated. The validated model will be implemented on Simulink RealTime, running on a SpeedGoat real-time target machine. This setup will ensure that the calculations of mooring forces and WEC responses can be performed in real time.

The hybrid simulation system will leverage WEC-Sim to calculate mooring forces using MoorDyn. These forces will be transmitted to a set of motors that actuate the mooring lines in the Large Wave Flume at Oregon State's O.H. Hinsdale Wave Lab. Motors attached to the mooring lines in the flume will be actuated to apply this force. A load cell will ensure that the correct force is always being applied.

Fig. 1. Illustration of the mooring truncation point, locations of actuation and sensing, and wave flume setup.

As the WEC moves, its displacement will be tracked using a Qualisys motion tracking system. This displacement data will be sent back to the SpeedGoat machine, which will feed it into the WEC-Sim model. The model will then compute the new mooring forces based on the updated displacement for the next time step, maintaining a continuous feedback loop between the simulation and the physical model. This interaction between the simulation and the physical model can be seen in Figure 2. Developing efficient algorithms for real-time data processing and feedback will be essential. This includes filtering sensor data to remove noise, updating the numerical model promptly, and recalculating forces within a tight timeframe to ensure the system responds accurately and swiftly to changes in the WEC's motion. The control algorithms will need to handle the high-frequency updates and ensure stability and precision in the force application.

Fig. 2. Feedback loop for real-time hybrid simulation scheme.

3. Conclusions and Future Work

Real-time hybrid simulation systems have so far been shown to have the computational speed to be viable in a hardware-in-the-loop setup and the integration of MoorDyn introduces more realistic non-linear dynamics into the testing environment. This allows for the accurate simulation of real-world conditions, including the intricate behaviors of mooring lines under varying wave forces. Implementing a system like the one proposed is not only feasible but also promising for advancing WEC testing and development. The computational capabilities of modern hybrid simulation systems, combined with the enhanced realism provided by MoorDyn, create a powerful tool for investigating and optimizing WEC designs. Moreover, the real-time aspect ensures that feedback loops between the simulated and physical components are maintained, allowing for continuous and adaptive adjustments based on real-time data. This dynamic interaction is crucial for accurately replicating the conditions that WECs will face in actual deployment scenarios.

Investigating the scalability of the hybrid simulation approach to larger WEC models and more complex mooring configurations will be a key focus. This includes testing the system with different WEC designs and varying water depths. Further development of this model will address the application range of the system across varied hydrodynamic bodies and behaviors, mooring configurations, and wave conditions. Additionally, ensuring the hybrid simulation system can handle variability in environmental conditions, such as changing wave patterns and unexpected disturbances, will be crucial for its practical application. One of the potential applications of this system is extreme condition testing that cannot be replicated using a simpler spring setup. Therefore, robustness is a key factor in the design of this system.

In addition to the real-time implementation on a SpeedGoat real-time target machine, a soft real-time approach will also be explored. In the case of soft real-time, an extra computer must be introduced in order to run MoorDyn external to the SpeedGoat. Soft real-time is commonly used in autopilot systems and spacecraft where the system continues to run even if a timestep is not able to execute in time. This is beneficial, and likely necessary, in several ways. First, MoorDyn's status as a dynamic library makes it hard or potentially impossible to perform real-time simulations directly in Simulink RealTime on the SpeedGoat (this approach is often called "hard" real-time). Second, soft real-time systems, unlike hard real-time systems, can tolerate some delays or variations in processing time. This flexibility can be advantageous in situations where slight delays do not critically affect the system's performance. Therefore, while using hard real-time may be a simpler approach in terms of the amount of hardware required, soft real-time may be the true key to success in this research.

Future testing will be done both in the O.H. Hinsdale wave flume and on a linear test bed. Testing is scheduled in the wave flume for December of 2025. Prior to this test campaign, the hybrid simulation setup will be tested on a linear test bed to ensure the real-time system is functioning properly and to determine any issues prior to wave tank testing. The linear test bed will allow for limited degree of freedom testing of the whole system to evaluate time delays, response accuracy, and system reliability. The strategy of using the linear test bed will significantly cut testing cost, streamline the wave flume testing process, and confirm that the system will work in a more controlled environment.

The hybrid simulation system will enable the testing of advanced mooring designs, including those with nonlinear characteristics and those intended for extreme conditions. This will help in optimizing mooring systems for various WEC deployment scenarios. In the future, this technology can be used by marine energy developers to more easily and realistically test their WECs. Also, comprehensive environmental and economic assessments of the hybrid simulation approach could provide insights into its feasibility and impact. This includes evaluating the potential for cost savings in WEC design and testing and assessing the environmental benefits of more efficient wave energy testing.

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